

Practice Oriented Science: UAE – RUSSIA – INDIA

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COGNITIVE APPROACH TO KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT AS TOOLS FOR DECISION-MAKING BY ECONOMIC ENTITIES

Larin Sergey Nikolaevich

Candidate of Technical Sciences, Leading Researcher

Central Economics and Mathematics Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences

Annotation. *The market transformation of the Russian economy entailed the need to adequately change the structure and management algorithms of economic entities of different scales and levels of aggregation. The general intellectualization of the processes of reproduction of various types of products and services makes it urgent to study approaches, methods and technologies for making management decisions. At the same time, information support for management processes of economic entities should be based on the use of fundamentally new methods of intelligent data analysis, systematically activating the potential of modern software and analytical tools. However, the current scope of their application is limited to a fairly narrow range of individual formalized management tasks. The current state of the national economy requires further development of the conceptual and methodological foundations for data analysis and optimization of the activities of management structures of economic entities in conditions of uncertainty.*

Keywords: *knowledge management, cognitive approach, tools, decision making, economic actors.*

Introduction.

The management system of economic entities (EE) can be represented as a hierarchical structure: information collection systems – decision support systems (information analysis systems) – decision-maker (DM). Many aspects of EE activities are accompanied by the collection of information, which is accumulated in databases (DB) on electronic and paper media, and sometimes in knowledge bases (KB). The analysis of this information focuses on identifying indicators-indexes, average values, or other indicators, usually inadequately reflecting the real situation in the studied system. In addition, the interrelationship and interdependence of data that can be used for management decision-making are practically not studied.

Main part.

Currently, EE management is carried out through special economic and social levers: tax rates, lending, investment, social payments, etc. However, often these measures are not systemic in nature and do not allow enterprises as economic entities to achieve their goals. The transition to new management technologies should be carried out gradually, complementing existing structures, systems and management methods. The modern paradigm is the replacement of an economy based on the use of natural resources with an economy based on knowledge [1].

It seems to us that in modern conditions, to support management decision-making by EE, it is advisable to use an approach based on a synthesis of the provisions of management theory, cybernetics, cognitive modeling, statistical and data mining. The practical implementation of this approach is based on the use of cognitive modeling of semi-structured problems to formalize the EE management system [2].

When managing a complex object characterized by quantitative and qualitative information, the following identification concept is proposed:

- 1) cognitive description of the object and its structural analysis;
- 2) impulse modeling of cognitive description, which allows one to evaluate the development scenarios of the subject;
- 3) identification of subsystems characterized by quantitative information;
- 4) building models using applied statistics and data mining;
- 5) coordination of cognitive models of EE and models obtained using methods of analysis of structured information;
- 6) in case of mismatch – return to point 4;
- 7) choice of control actions;
- 8) control of the management process;
- 9) assessment of control and, if necessary, return to paragraphs 1÷3 [3].

To implement the concept described above, it is necessary to formalize the ES management system. The result is the construction of a metaset model of the corresponding system:

$$M = \{M_o(Y, U, P), M_o(X), M_{Ys\chi}, M_D(Q), M_{MO}, M_{ME}, M_U, A, M_n\}, \quad (1)$$

where $M_o(Y, U, P)$ is an identifying model of the system (for example, the labor market), in which: vector Y – endogenous variables $y \in Y \subseteq E^m$, characterizing the phase state of the object (for example, income, investments, number of personnel, etc.); U – vector of controlled variables $u \in U \subseteq E^r$, (for example, buildings and structures, energy costs, costs of updating fixed assets, investments in education, investments in the production of certain types of products, etc.); P – vector of available resources $p \in P \subseteq E^n$ (for example, fixed assets, profit, quantitative estimates of basic types of resources);

$M_o(X)$ – environmental model (regional economic system), X – exogenous quantities (for example, taking into account the influence of environmental factors, conditions of exchange between economic entities);

$M_{YSZ} = \{M_{SZ}M_{YS}\}$ – model of interaction between subject and environment (M_{SZ} – models of connection with the environment at the input, M_{YS} – models of systems with connections with the environment at the output);

$M_D(Q)$ – model of object behavior, Q – disturbing influences;

M_{MQ} and M_{ME} – models for measuring the state of an object and the environment (for example, production development programs, data acquisition plans, organization of measurements);

M_U – a model of the control (regulatory) system (for example, a regional regulatory system), it is not included in the set if only the problems of studying the control object are solved;

A – the rule for selecting processes for changing an object;

M_n – a model of the “observer” (researcher, expert cognitive scientist), which allows taking into account changes in the understanding (cognition) of the object being studied by the researcher and synthesizing the methodology of research and decision-making.

The solution to the system control problem is considered in the following sequence:

1) determination of the control goal and control actions Qn , allowing to achieve the set goal;

2) maintaining the system in the achieved state until a new goal appears.

Typically, an analysis of the current state of a complex situation is performed by a decision maker in the following stages:

1) selection of models for managing target factors in order to ensure the desired behavior of the EE;

2) assessment of possible changes in situations in the future;

3) assessment of possible problems.

Modeling EE behavior can be represented as a set of interacting dynamic processes occurring in real time. Modeling with different types of graphs reflects the sequence of state changes, and time actually has no sense of time. This occurs when considering digraphs and weighted digraphs. Accounting for time in the cognitive model is based on the use of modified functional graphs – MF graphs. To do this, you need to define:

1) the set of vertices V of the graph G , representing a set of factors of the modeled object;

2) many arcs of factors that determine their influence on each other;

3) QE column G representing impact aggregates $\subseteq \{Imp\}$ – impulses representing external disturbances;

4) ε – extreme accuracy of calculations [4].

A disturbance received at one of the vertices spreads along the chain to the rest, intensifying or fading. Thus, the values of variables at the vertices of the graph can change under the influence of incoming disturbances.

Let's consider the rule for changing parameters at vertices at time t_{n+1} .

If the parameter x_i depends on the time $x_i=x_i(t)$, then it is possible to determine the process of propagation of disturbances along the graph, i.e., the transition of the system from state $t-1$ to $t, t+1, \dots$

If the value $x_i(t+1)$ at vertex V_i is influenced by previous values $x_i(t)$ and vertices adjacent to V_i , and vertex V_i is adjacent to V_j , and $p_j(t)$ is the change at vertex V_j at time t , then the influence of this change to parameter x_i at time t , depending on the sign of the arc connecting V_i and V_j , will be described by the function $\pm p_j(t)$.

Let there be several vertices V_j adjacent to V_i , then the process of propagation of a disturbance through the graph is determined by the formula

$$x_i(t+1) = x_i(t) + \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} f(x_i, x_j, e_j) p_j(t), \tag{2}$$

where $x(0)$ are known initial values at all vertices;

$p(0)$ – initial vector of disturbances.

Typically, modeling is carried out in steps or pulses, i.e. a certain change is specified in one of the vertices, which initiates all vertices associated with it. These vertices are called activating.

The simplest version of representing the function f_{ij} between the vertices V_j, V_i is the coefficients $\lambda_{ji}, \omega_{ji}$, characterizing the sign (λ_{ji} : “+” or “-”) and degree of influence ω_{ji} vertex parameter V_j to vertex parameter V_i ; we will represent the function $p_j(t)$ of the influence of a change in the vertex V_i adjacent to V_j in the form of an impulse:

$$p(n) = x(n+1) - x(n),$$

where $x(n), x(n+1)$ are the values of the indicator at vertex V_i at simulation steps at the moment $t=n$ and the following $t=n+1$.

Then formula (1) is transformed to the form:

$$x_i(n+1) = x_i(n) + \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} \lambda_{ji} \omega_{ji} [x_j(n+1) - x_j(n)]. \tag{3}$$

The coefficients ω_{ij} , which characterize the mutual influence of adjacent vertices, are determined statistically or expertly.

In such models it is possible to introduce lags - delays in the transmission of impact along each arc.

The rule (PR) for changing parameters at the vertices at time t_{n+1} , if impulses arrived at the vertices at time t_n , looks like this:

$$x_{v_i}(n+1) = x_{v_i}(n) + \sum_{v_j: e=e_{ij} \in E}^{k-1} f(x_i, x_j, e_{ij}) P_j(n) + Q_i(n+1) \tag{4}$$

$$P_{v_i}(n+1) = \sum_{v_j: e=e_{ij} \in E}^{k-1} f(x_i, x_j, e_{ij}) P_j(n) + Q_i(n+1). \tag{5}$$

The model of an impulse process is a tuple $\langle F, Q, PR \rangle$, where F is the F -graph, $F = \langle (V, E), X, W \rangle$, $Q = Q(t_n)$ is the sequence of disturbing influences, PR is the rule of change parameters.

The model representation of the system $\langle t_n, S_n, B_n \rangle$ is the sequence $\langle n, X(t_n), Q(t_n) \rangle$.

Let's consider a mathematical model of impulse processes in matrix form (on signed graphs). Let us introduce the following notation:

$Q_t = \{q_{it}\}_{i=1}^k$, $t=0, 1, 2, \dots$, is the vector of external impulses q_{it} introduced into vertices v_i at time t ;

$X_t = \{x_{it}\}_{i=1}^k$, $t=0, 1, 2, \dots$, – vector of values of parameters x_{it} of vertices v_i at time t ;

$R_t = \{\Delta_{it}\}_{i=1}^k$ – vector of vertex parameters at time t , which is given by the equation:

$$R_t = X_t - X_{t-1}I, \quad t=1, 2, 3, \dots$$

Then changes in the parameters of the vertices can be specified by the following equation:

$$X_t = X_{t-1}I + AR_{t-1} + Q_{t-1} \quad (6)$$

From the last equation we obtain the expression for R_t :

$$R_t = A^{t-1}Q_0 + A^{t-2}Q_1 + \dots + AQ_{t-2} + IQ_{t-1}, \quad (7)$$

where I is the identity matrix.

The methodology for modeling the management of economic entities based on qualitative and quantitative information should be based on the following principles:

1) the principle of external additions (the criterion for constructing a mathematical model is the purpose of modeling - obtaining a forecast, describing patterns in the data, obtaining a model for management);

2) the principle of cyclical data analysis when putting forward and testing various hypotheses;

3) the principle of freedom of choice of decisions;

4) the principle of non-final decisions;

5) the principle of multiplicity of mathematical models.

Based on these principles, an enlarged scheme for modeling the EE management process is proposed (see Fig. 1).

At the first stage, the expert formulates research problems and proposes a system of concepts. Depending on the available information and its changes, goals and concepts may also undergo changes.

At the second stage, concepts are identified, with:

If the concepts are qualitative, then the task comes down to cognitive modeling based on the algebraic-geometric approach.

If the concepts are quantitative, then tabular data analysis methods are used and the available information is identified in the following sequence:

1. If there is a database, they focus on the Knowledge discovery in databases (KDD) and Data mining (DM) methods.

2. If there are small amounts of unrelated information, decision makers focus on methods of applied statistics and data analysis.

3. If there are quantitative and qualitative concepts, it is necessary to move on to analysis at a qualitative level (step 1), and if it is possible to identify a subsystem with quantitative concepts, go to step 2.

Next, cognitive models are built in the form of graphs and (or) numerical models, they are verified (substantive assessment), results are analyzed, decisions are made and recommendations are developed for decision makers of economic entities.

Figure 1. Enlarged scheme for modeling the EE management process.

Conclusion.

As a result of the research, an approach to modeling the EE management process was proposed, based on the use of available quantitative and qualitative information and implemented in the form of an enlarged scheme for modeling the management decision support process.

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